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TEACHERS' VOLITION, INSTRUCTION AND CORRECTION STRATEGIES FOR TEACHING STUDENTS' WITH BEHAVIOURAL PROBLEMS IN GENDER- SPECIFIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE- NIGERIA

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Abstract

Teachers' volition, relevant instruction and correction strategies are vital factors in capturing students' interest, attention, commitment and positive emotions in a learning situation which of course will allow them less time to engage in behavioural problems. The study adopted descriptive research design to investigate teachers' volition, instruction and correction strategies for teaching students' with behavioural problems in gender-specific secondary schools in Anambra state-Nigeria. Seven research questions guided the study. The population comprised all the 1,825 teachers in male secondary schools in Anambra state. A sample of 80 teachers was randomly selected from the schools using simple random sampling technique. A researcher-developed instrument named "Teachers' Volition, Instruction and Correction Strategies" (TVICS) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by specialists in Education. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha method and an alpha coefficient of 0.78 was obtained. The research questions were answered using frequencies, percentages and statistical weighted mean. The result of the study revealed that most teachers' lack volition to teach students' with behavioural problems. Also the instruction and correction strategies employed by majority of the teachers do not trigger intrinsic motivation and positive emotions of the students' which are vital for transformation of behavioural problems. Based on the findings, the researchers' recommended the use of instructional strategies like co-operative learning, games/simulations, project method, field trips/excursions, role playing as well as correction strategies like premack principle, praise and reinforcement among others.

Keywords: *Teachers' volition, instruction strategies, correction strategies and students' with behavioural problems.*

Introduction

The teacher is one of the principal elements in a formal education. The role of teachers in education is significant most especially in the lives of the students' they teach. The teachers role include instruction- teaching to impart knowledge, guidance- directing and proffering advice and suggestions to challenges/problems and role of correction which implies channeling a students behaviour to the acceptable norms. These roles are paramount for every effectual learning environment and academic achievement (Europass Teacher Academy, 2022). Giving credence to this assertion is Javier, Antonio and Sonia (2024); Sanchez-Mendias, Minan-Espigares and Rodriguez-Fernandez (2024) who opined that the teacher's function in the teaching and learning sector should go beyond content delivery to building necessary capacities stipulated in the education guideline/policy in the students.

In the context of this research work, the researchers explain a teacher as a person that help a student to learn by imparting knowledge to them OR one who teach students. The teacher may be likened to a “builder” because he/she is saddled with the responsibility of moulding, shaping and transforming the lives of students. Divyansh (2021) described a teacher as one who builds inquisitiveness, mastery and insight through the exercise of teaching.

Some authors and researchers have attempted explanation of teaching according to their perspectives. Ekramul (2022) opined that teaching is an activity that promotes learning, transfer of knowledge and skills. It is also meant to give special assistance to accomplish both the personal and public needs in education. Samar (2022) noted that teaching is an inter play between the teacher and the student based on a course of study. Teaching is geared towards students’ acquisition of knowledge and skills, development of good disposition and self determination (Lisedunetwork, 2023). Giving credence to the above assertion, Divyansh (2021) noted that teaching is an action involving equipping students with new information, provide for ingenuity, building relationship skills and more so helping parents in their children education.

In the context of this study, the researchers explain teaching as interaction of the teacher and the students using various approaches to enhance their understanding, retention, recall of concepts as well as transfer of knowledge. For a teacher to deliver maximally in any teaching-learning situation, he/she must have a good knowledge of the subject matter/content, approaches/methods, students’ differences and problems. The teacher should have command of the learning environment (Hudson, 2024). Teaching is not only about imparting knowledge to the learner but includes character and behaviour transformation to raise a healthy personality. The academic certificate given at the completion of any programme in any formal educations testifies to this assertion.

The main laboratory in a teaching and learning event is the classroom. The kind of learning that take place in a classroom refers to formal learning which is organized in an orderly manner based on a stipulated curriculum as opposed to informal learning which can take place in unsentimental surroundings such as the home, church among others without guided approach (Valeria, Lidia, Giselle and Susan, 2024). Students from different background, with different attitudes and behaviours are found in the same classroom. In line with the above assertion, Future Educators (2021) observed that a classroom comprise all manner of students both well behaved and ill behaved but stressed that the later should be specially handled to inculcate acceptable character, emotions and behaviours in them.

Behavioural problems such as bullying, stealing, stubbornness, truancy, experimenting with alcohol and drugs, homosexuals, lesbian, lateness to school, truancy, and examination malpractice among others has been proven by research such as Millicent (2022), Roisin (2019), Monu-Borkala (2021) and Desappriyan (2022) to be rampant among secondary school students’ especially male gender. Jayne (2021) observed that young children often in response to some events, challenges and situations exhibit abnormal conduct but emphasized that once this violates the characteristics of the child’s developmental stage, it becomes a behavioural problem. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2023) explained that sometimes children could behave unruly but it is a behavioural problem when it is repeated often and seems unconventional for the chronological age of the child.

Behavioural problems in the classroom as observed by McGillicuddy (2024) pose a lot of challenge to the teacher. It hinders class progress, students’ achievement, academic goals and impactful learning. To secure impactful teaching for impactful learning, certain factors must be in place. One of such factors is the teacher’s volition. In every aspect of life ranging from social, marriage, career and academics, willingness is a strong force to success. Volition is a mindset that makes an individual to be focused, diligent, persevering and enduring all oppositions to success. Supporting this statement, Jackie (2023) opined that in as much as diligence, steadfastness and optimistic are vital keys to success, volition remains the most vital antidote.

Qin (2014) asserted that teachers’ volition is an indispensable attribute for a successful and productive pedagogy. Clio (2020) supporting the above statement affirmed that an enthusiastic teacher has daring vigour to apprehend attentiveness thus increasing students eager and desire to engage in learning exercise. When students’ interest are secured, academic engagement is guaranteed and thus less time to engage in behavioural problems. Hawthorne (2021) asserted that motivation is a vital element for effective instruction. It builds positive behaviour, healthy personality as well as secures students attention in education. Clio (2021) noted that only enthusiastic teachers can influence students’ interest and academic resilience. Okeke, , Onyekwere, Okorie, Anene and Umennabuikwe (2023) affirmed that teachers’ volition birth readiness for instruction and discipline.

Alongside volition of teachers is use of adequate and effective instruction strategies in teaching. It is an undisputable fact in teaching-learning process that when a student is active, he/she is engaging in his academics but when the student is passive, he/she will be engaged with other things outside his/her academics and to a great extent the instructional procedures, approaches and methods used by a teacher determines the activeness or passiveness of a learner. Jill (2023); Joshua (2023) and Blakeley (2024) explained instructional strategies as the approaches used by teachers to achieve pedagogical goals. They attempted the classification of these instructional

methods into five types namely: first-hand, secondary, exploratory, interactional and individualistic. Michelle (2022) defined instructional strategies as tutelage methods employed by classroom teachers to accomplish their tasks. Drew (2023) defined instructional strategies as the foundation of any instruction which includes all the approaches and skills utilized by teachers to solve educational problems encountered by students thus ensuring their greater scale of acquisition of experiences and application.

Another factor vital in the classroom for impactful teaching and learning as well as good behaviours among the students is the teachers' correction strategies. In the context of this research work, the researchers' explained correction strategies as all measures taken by the classroom teacher to reduce/weaken undesired behaviours and increase/strengthen desired behaviours. Creative learning outcome requires understanding of students' challenges and willingness to handle them. This is vital as noted by Ellie (2018) that one of the greatest challenges confronting a classroom teacher is behavioural problems exhibited by the students because they hinder class effectiveness. Ellie further noted that all behaviour is a form of transmission and thus need for the teacher to have proper training and discipline strategy to deal with them. Wirawani and Pang (2015) stressed that teachers' expertise in instruction and correction strategies are vital for constructive learning.

The researchers' experiences during their career as secondary school teachers and observation of teaching and learning process in some secondary schools in Anambra state reveal the teachers' use of such instruction strategies like explanation, note copying by the teacher, note copying by the class prefect in absence and presence of the teacher, take home assignment and class exercise. Also the teachers' employ correction strategies like cutting grass, digging a pit, fetching water, kneeling down with hands up, suspension and expulsion. As mentioned earlier, accomplishment of goals and objectives of teaching and learning process requires teachers' willingness (zeal, passion, commitment and empathy among others) to impart the desired knowledge in the students' as well as shape their character and behaviour. Without volition on the teachers' part, a student with behavioural problem is often ignored. The researchers' strongly believe that no enthusiastic teacher will allow a student that passed through his/her tutelage to be a nuisance and such certain positive steps towards shaping the student behaviour must be utilized.

It is against this background that the researchers' intend to investigate teachers' volition, instruction and correction strategies for teaching students' with behavioural problems in gender-specific secondary schools in Anambra state with a view to proffering solutions.

To give direction to this study, the following research questions were formulated:

1. What is the extent of teachers' volition to teach students' with behavioural problems in gender-specific secondary schools in Anambra state?
2. What instruction strategies are used by teachers' in teaching and learning process in gender-specific secondary schools in Anambra state?
3. What are the correction strategies utilized by teachers for handling students' with behavioural problems in gender-specific secondary schools in Anambra state?
4. To what extent do the instruction and correction strategies used by teachers' transform behavioural problems of students in gender-specific secondary schools in Anambra state?
5. What strategies could be adopted to stimulate teachers' volition to employ adequate and effective instruction and correction measures to reduce behavioural problems among students' in gender-specific secondary schools in Anambra state?
6. What possible instruction strategies could be effective for securing students' curiosity and interest in academic goals to minimize their indulgence in behavioural problems?
7. What are the possible correction measures to be adopted by the teachers to handle students with behavioral problems to minimize the occurrence?

Method

The study adopted descriptive research design. Data was collected from a sample considered to be representative of the population. The study was carried out in male secondary schools in Anambra state-Nigeria. The choice of male secondary schools was borne out of findings from review of related literatures that behavioural problems are common with boys/males than girls/females. The population comprised all the 1, 825 teachers in male secondary schools in Anambra state. Using purposive random sampling techniques, the researchers' selected 2 male schools from each of the 6 education zones (Awka, Onitsha, Otuocha, Aguata, Nnewi and Ogidi) in Anambra state giving a total of 12 schools. Using simple random sampling technique, 80 teachers were selected from the chosen schools.

A researcher-developed instrument named "Teachers' Volition, Instruction and Correction Strategies" (TVICS) was used for data collection. The instrument was structured on a modified 4-point likert scale ranging from

strongly agree, agree, disagree to strongly disagree. Specialists in Education validated the instrument for face and content adequacy. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha and overall reliability of 0.78 was obtained.

The administration of the instrument was done through direct delivery approach. Data collected were analyzed using frequencies, percentages and statistical weighted mean. Acceptance point for the items was 2.50 and any mean below 2.50 was regarded as rejected.

Results and Findings

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage of Extent of Teachers' Volition to Teach Students' with Behavioural Problems.

N = 80

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Rarely	11	13.8
Often	11	13.8
Always	09	11.3
Never	49	61.3
Total	80	100.2

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage of teachers' volition in teaching students' with behavioural problems in gender-specific secondary schools in Anambra state as follows: Rarely = 13.8%, Often = 13.8%, Always = 11.3% and Never = 61.3%.

Table 2: Mean Scores of Teachers on the Instruction Strategies Used for Teaching Students With Behavioural Problems.

N = 80.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	X	Decision
1	Explanation	30	20	23	07	2.91	Agree
2	Note copying by the teacher	30	22	18	10	2.90	Agree
3	Note copying by the class prefect	28	26	16	10	2.79	Agree
4	Discussion	10	20	26	24	2.20	Disagree
5	Project method	10	17	28	35	2.28	Disagree
6	Games/Simulations.	05	10	25	40	1.75	Disagree
7	Repetition method	15	09	26	30	2.11	Disagree
8	Assignment method	10	35	25	10	2.56	Agree
9	Experimental method	04	11	24	41	1.73	Disagree
10	Drill and practice	08	17	23	32	2.01	Disagree

Table 2 shows that the teachers' with a mean score of 2.50 agreed to be using only the following instructional methods namely explanation, note copying by the teacher, note copying by the class prefect and assignment for teaching students' with behavioural problems. Other instructional methods like discussion, project method, games, repetition, experimental and drill and practice had mean scores below 2.50 and so depict rejection by the teachers.

Table 3: Mean Scores of Teachers on the Correction Strategies Used for Handling Students' With Behavioural Problems.

N = 80.

11	Flogging	24	26	20	10	2.78	Agree
12	Kneeling down with hands up.	28	27	15	10	2.91	Agree
13	Cutting grass	36	24	15	05	2.78	Agree
14	Digging a pit	35	21	14	10	3.01	Agree
15	Lying down on the floor.	32	28	15	05	3.09	Agree
16	Picking pieces of paper in the school premises.	30	32	10	08	3.05	Agree
17	Running round the school compound for several times.	40	25	10	05	3.25	Agree
18	Public/open shame.	35	25	15	05	3.15	Agree
19	Derogatory song by the class.	30	22	18	12	2.88	Agree
20	Suspension	25	32	13	10	2.90	Agree

21	Expulsion	30	25	15	10	2.94	Agree
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From the result in table 3 above, the teachers' with a mean score of 2.50 and above agreed that all the 11 items in the instrument which include flogging, kneeling down with hands up, cutting grass, digging a pit, suspension, open shame and expulsion among others were among the correction measures they use in handling students' with behavioural problems.

Table 4: Mean Scores of Teachers on Suggested Strategies that Could be Adopted to Enhance their Volition in Teaching Students' with Behavioural Problems.

N = 80

22	Improved and attractive welfare package.	30	22	18	12	2.88	Agree
23	On- time promotion	35	25	15	05	3.15	Agree
24	On- time payment of monthly salary and promotion arrears.	40	25	10	05	3.25	Agree
25	Appointment in school boards and ministries of education.	30	32	10	08	3.05	Agree
26	On- time payment of retirement benefits and pensions.	32	28	15	05	3.09	Agree
27	Provision of staff quarters in the school premises.	35	28	17	10	2.72	Agree
28	Provision of soft loans and grants to challenged teachers.	36	24	15	05	2.78	Agree
29	Provision of low income houses at affordable price.	28	27	15	10	2.91	Agree
30	Study leave with full salary	24	26	20	10	2.78	Agree

Table 4 shows from the mean scores of 2.50 and above that the teachers in gender-specific secondary schools in Anambra state-Nigeria agreed that such measures like improved and attractive salary, on-time promotion, on-time payment of monthly salary and promotion arrears, appointment in school boards and ministries of education, on-time payment of retirement benefits and pensions among others if adhered to by the government will boost their volition to teach students with behavioural problems.

Table 5: Mean Scores of Teachers on Suggested Instruction Strategies that Could Be Effective for Teaching Students' with Behavioural Problems.

N = 80

31	Field trips/excursion method	35	26	14	05	3.14	Agree
32	Cooperative learning method	38	22	12	08	3.12	Agree
33	Class discussion	28	26	16	10	2.79	Agree
34	Experimental method	36	28	06	10	3.12	Agree
35	Role play method	30	20	23	07	2.91	Agree
36	Computer based instruction method.	40	25	10	05	3.25	Agree
37	Problem solving method	30	22	18	12	2.88	Agree
38	Plays/games method	28	27	15	10	2.91	Agree
39	Project method	30	25	15	10	2.94	Agree
40	Drill and practice method	25	32	13	10	2.90	Agree

Results in table 5 above shows that all the suggested instructional measures in the instrument has a mean score of 2.50 and above thus depicting teachers' agreement to their effectiveness in securing attention and interest of students' in academic pursuit thus minimizing their behavioural problems.

Table 6: Mean Scores of Teachers' on Suggested Correction Measures for Handling Students' with Behavioural Problems.

N = 80.

41	Model and promote desirable behaviours.	32	28	15	05	3.09	Agree
42	Use of praise	40	25	10	05	3.25	Agree
43	Use of reinforcements	10	35	25	10	2.56	Agree
44	Focus more on rewards than punishment.	30	20	23	07	2.91	Agree

45	Employ premack principles	36	28	06	10	3.12	Agree
46	Establish a class code of conduct	26	22	20	10	2.85	Agree
47	Establish relationship with deviant students.	35	20	15	10	3.00	Agree
48	Adopt peer tutor technique	40	25	10	05	3.25	Agree
49	Engage parents with positive communication opportunities.	39	25	10	07	3.18	Agree
50	Talk to problem students privately	30	22	18	10	2.90	Agree

Results in table 6 above shows that the 10 suggested correctional measures which among others include model and promote desirable behaviour, use of praise, use of rewards, use of reinforcement and use of premack principle had a mean score of 2.50 and above. The researchers' therefore conclude the teachers' agreement with the suggested correction measures.

Discussion

Findings of the study revealed that most teachers' in gender specific secondary schools in Anambra state-Nigeria lack volition for teaching students' with behavioural problems. The researchers' may attribute this to some experiences which they also encountered during their secondary school career ranging from non challant attitude of government to educational sector with the attendant effects such as poor teachers welfare package, unnecessary withholding of promotion, delay in payment of monthly salaries, retirement benefits and pensions among others. All these conditions put together brings untold hardship, suffering and even psychological and mental health problems to the teachers thus affecting their willingness to teach. It is an undisputable fact that good welfare package stirs willingness/enthusiasm which is vital for securing students' academic engagement and behavioural problems are reduced when students are engaged with their studies. Supporting this assertion is Okeke et al (2023) that adequate motivate of teachers stir encouragement and morale to work without coercion thus ever ready to solve students' problems as well as liase with parents in training of their children.

Findings of the study also revealed that most instruction strategies used by the teachers lack the tendency, force and power to capture participation of the students in a lesson but rather makes them passive learners. The researchers' wish to state that only activity and practical based instruction approach will be capable of securing a student curiosity, attention and interest and thus less time for behavioural problems. Put in another way, when a student is not or less busy, there is tendency for him/her to be a devil's workshop. Furthermore, the correction measures used by the teachers are punishment strategies. Educationists strongly believe that punishment has a destroying than building, shaping and moulding effect and thus could be applied as last resort after all reinforcement strategies has failed.

The findings of the study revealed that such instruction approaches like field trips, cooperative learning, class discussion, experimentation method and computer based instruction among could be effective for teaching students, with behavioural problems to secure their attention and interest in academic goals. This agrees with the findings of Michelle (2022), Jill (2023) who enumerated such instructional strategies like collaborative learning, excursion, amusement, exploratory and character playing as effective in boosting resilience and academic engagement among students.

Furthermore, the findings of the study shows that correction measures like praise, reward, punishment, reinforcement, establishing relationship with students, information to parents and application of premack principle can help reduce behavioural problems in students. This findings align with Millicent (2022), Joshua, (2023), Michelle (2022) and Future Educators (2021) who noted that students' with behavioural problems can be shaped and transformed using strategies like award, applaud, good rapport, giving first hand information to parents, avoid open rebuke, and being a role model among others.

Conclusion

The researchers' conclude as follows:

1. Most teachers' in gender specific secondary schools lack volition to teach students with behavioural problems.
2. Most of the instruction strategies used by the teachers makes the student a passive rather than active learner and thus much time to engage in behavioural problems.
3. The correction measures employed by the teachers' are mostly punishment which is detrimental to raising a healthy personality.
4. Instruction methods such as field trips/excursion, role playing and cooperating learning among others were suggested for effective teaching of students with behavioural problems.

5. Correction strategies such as praise, reward and reinforcement among others were suggested as possible approaches for handling behavioural problems.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers' recommend as follows:

1. Government at all levels should redress their steps by giving the education sector the desired priority thus enforcing the attractiveness of teachers welfare package so as to secure their volition to put in their best in teaching and learning process.
2. Job seekers are admonished to engage the "choice" and not "chance/opportunity" mentality when applying for a teaching job. No one can deliver in a profession or career where he/she lack interest, knowledge and efficiency.
3. Teachers are admonished to use reward, praise and reinforcement instead of punishment in handling behavioural problems. This is because the later will only succeed in producing a hardened social misfit and nuisance to the society.

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